

Organic Pesticides. Part XIV. Preparation of Some Fluoroaryloxy Fatty Acids and Their Mercury Derivatives

K. C. Joshi and S. C. Bahel

Several fluoroaryloxy fatty acids and their mercury derivatives have been prepared as antifungal agents.

The present work has been undertaken with a view to synthesising aromatic fluorine compounds which may act as potential pest-control chemicals. The synthesis of a number of fluoroaryloxy fatty acids and their mercury derivatives has been reported earlier¹. The compounds, when evaluated for their toxicity against *Alternaria solani*, provided encouraging results². The work has therefore been extended to synthesising a large number of fluorine-substituted aryloxy fatty acids and their mercury derivatives as possible fungicides against a wide range of fungi. The results of bioassay will be communicated later.

The fluoroaryloxy fatty acids have been obtained as usual by condensing *p*-fluorophenol, 2-bromo-4-fluorophenol, and 2-chloro-4-fluorophenol with halogenated fatty acids in presence of caustic soda solution³. The fluoroaryloxy fatty acids have been mercurated by the method described by Friend⁴ and their mono-mercurated derivatives obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Bromo-4-fluorophenol was obtained by the treatment of *p*-fluorophenol (25 g., prepared according to the method of Finger *et al.*⁵) with bromine (36 g.) in CS₂ medium, b.p. 59-60°/0.5 mm. Finger *et al.*⁵ reported b.p. 89°/1 mm. The compound was further characterised by determination of its molecular weight ebullioscopically. (Found: M.W., 194. Calc. for C₆H₄OBrF: M.W., 190.9).

2-Chloro-4-fluorophenol was prepared by bubbling chlorine gas (27 g.) into *p*-fluorophenol (84 g.) in presence of iron filings at room temperature for 7½ hours, b.p. 60-62°/0.1-1 mm. Finger *et al.*⁵ reported b.p. 88°/40 mm. The compound was further characterised by determination of its molecular weight ebullioscopically. (Found: M.W., 149. Calc. for C₆H₄OClF: M.W., 146.45).

Fluoroaryloxy acids were prepared as reported earlier¹ and characterised by determination of their neutralisation equivalents. The compounds obtained are recorded in Table I.

1. Joshi and Bahel, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 365.
2. Joshi *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21C**, 315.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1555.
4. "Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. XI, Part I.
5. Finger *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 94.

ORGANIC PESTICIDES

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Fluoroaryloxy acid.	B.P.	Yield.	Neut. equiv. Found.	Reqd.	Formula.	M.P.	Found.	%Hg.	Reqd.
1.	<i>p</i> - <i>Fp</i> -valeric	160°/0.3 mm	60%	211.8	212.0	F.C ₆ H ₃ (-O.CH.C ₃ H ₇ .CO ₂).Hg	210°(d)	48.16	48.78	
2.	<i>p</i> - <i>Fp</i> -caproic	146°/0.1	56	225.7	226.0	F.C ₆ H ₃ (-O.CH.C ₄ H ₉ .CO ₂).Hg	260°(d)	47.76	47.17	
3.	<i>p</i> - <i>Fp</i> -caprylic	140°/0.01	33	253.4	254.0	F.C ₆ H ₃ (-O.CH.C ₆ H ₁₃ .CO ₂).Hg	235°(d)	44.65	44.24	
4.	2-Bromo-4- <i>Fp</i> -propionic	140°/0.05	50	262.5	263.0	F.Br.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₃ H ₇ .CO ₂).Hg	250°(d)	42.86	43.38	
5.	2-Bromo-4- <i>Fp</i> -butyric	170°/3	56	276.3	277.0	F.Br.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₄ H ₉ .CO ₂).Hg	*	41.85	42.10	
6.	2-Bromo-4- <i>Fp</i> -valeric	165°/1	55	291.5	291.0	F.Br.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₅ H ₇ .CO ₂).Hg	*	41.70	40.98	
7.	2-Bromo-4- <i>Fp</i> -caproic	180°/4	52	314.1	315.0	F.Br.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₆ H ₁₁ .CO ₂).Hg	300	40.65	30.75	
8.	2-Bromo-4- <i>Fp</i> -caprylic	165°/1	49	342.2	343.0	F.Br.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₈ H ₁₅ .CO ₂).Hg	*	37.23	37.66	
9.	2-Chloro-4- <i>Fp</i> -propionic	145°/0.2	58	218.1	218.5	F.Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₃ H ₇ .CO ₂).Hg	*	47.56	48.01	
10.	2-Chloro-4- <i>Fp</i> -butyric	155°/1	63	231.0	232.5	F.Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₄ H ₉ .CO ₂).Hg	*	45.89	46.45	
11.	2-Chloro-4- <i>Fp</i> -valeric	144°/0.01	48	245.8	246.5	F.Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₅ H ₇ .CO ₂).Hg	*	44.29	44.90	
12.	2-Chloro-4- <i>Fp</i> -caproic	150°/1	51	261.0	260.5	F.Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₆ H ₁₁ .CO ₂).Hg	*	43.75	43.43	
13.	2-Chloro-4- <i>Fp</i> -caprylic	160°/0.05	40	287.9	288.5	F.Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (-O.CH.C ₈ H ₁₅ .CO ₂).Hg	220	40.96	41.27	

N.B. *Fp* denotes fluorophenoxxy. d=decomposed

*Did not melt.

Mercuration of Fluoroaryloxy Fatty Acids.—The fluoroaryloxy fatty acids were mercurated by the methods of Friend⁴ and Sen and Joshi¹. A mixture of equimolecular quantities of yellow mercuric oxide in acetic acid and fluoroaryloxy fatty acid in ethanol was heated over a low flame till a sandy powder separated. The time required for the reaction varied from 2 to 6 hours. The precipitate was filtered and repeatedly washed successively with boiling water, hot dilute acetic acid, and hot ethanol.

The results of the analysis¹ indicate that mono-mercurated anhydrides of fluoroaryloxy fatty acids are formed. The mercury derivatives prepared have been listed in Table I.

One of the authors (S.C.B.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship.

ORGANIC CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
GORAKHPUR UNIVERSITY,
GORAKHPUR, U.P.

Received September 29, 1962.